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OR055

SLR_003 - SOLAR PHOTOCATALYTIC DECOLORIZATION OF AZO DYE SOLUTIONS USING NANOPARTICULATED Nb₂O₅

Alexsandro J. dos Santos, Luana M. B. Batista, Carlos A. Martínez-Huitle, Sergi Garcia-Segura, Ana P. M. Alves

In this work, Nb₂O₅ nanoparticles were applied as photocatalysts to evaluate the discoloration of the dye methyl orange using solar radiation. These nanoparticles were characterized by analysis XRD, SEM, FTIR, BET, UV-vis. In order to analyse the photocatalytic efficiency of Nb₂O₅, dye, H₂O₂, Nb₂O₅ concentrations and pH have been evaluated. The best operating conditions were 1 g L⁻¹ of Nb₂O₅, 5 mg L⁻¹ of methyl orange and 0.025 M of H₂O₂. The reuse of the catalyst was also addressed, determining that Nb₂O₅ particles maintained their efficiency after five times.

OR056

SLR_005 - COUPLED SEMICONDUCTOR PHOTO-FENTON'S TREATMENT OF REFRACTORY CHLOROPHENOLIC POLLUTANT USING Fe-TiO₂ and C-Fe-TiO₂ NANOPARTICLES UNDER NATURAL SUNLIGHT

Palanivelu Kandasamy, Jeevitha Raji Rathinavelu,

The present work focused on the synthesis of TiO₂ nanoparticles and tailor its solar photochemical properties by iron doping and carbon-iron co-doping. The synthesized catalysts were employed for the clean and green destruction of 2,4-dichlorophenol by coupled semiconductor photo-Fenton's process under natural sunlight. The synthesized catalysts were characterized by XRD, HR-SEM, EDX, UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy and BET surface area analysis. The average crystallite size of pure TiO₂ was in the range of 30-33 nm and that of Fe-TiO₂ and C-Fe TiO₂ nanotitania was in the range of 7-13 nm respectively. Coupled photo-Fenton's degradation of 2,4-DCP was favourable at pH 3 and H₂O₂ concentration as low as 9.9 mM was sufficient for effective mineralization of 2,4-DCP. Complete degradation of 2,4-DCP was possible till very low solar intensity of 20 kiloLUX.

OR057

SLR_006 - PHOTO-FENTON DEGRADATION OF A HERBICIDE USING THE FERRIOXALATE COMPLEX FOR PH CONDITIONS CLOSE TO NEUTRALITY: LABORATORY AND SOLAR PILOT-PLANT REACTOR.

Leandro O. Conte; Agustina V. Schenone; Orlando M. Alfano

A theoretical and experimental study of the photo-Fenton degradation of herbicide 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) is presented. A kinetic model derived from a reaction sequence is proposed using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source, for conditions of pH close to neutrality. Operating the system under simulated solar radiation, with high radiation level and the highest concentration of hydrogen peroxide (HP), the conversion of 2,4-D after 180 min of reaction was close to 100% over the full range of working temperatures. Moreover, for all the tests performed using the solar reactor, complete destruction of 2,4-D and 2,4-DCP (the main intermediate, 2,4-dichlorophenol) is obtained in only 75 and 120 min of reaction, respectively.

PHOTO-FENTON DEGRADATION OF A HERBICIDE USING THE FERROXALATE COMPLEX FOR PH CONDITIONS CLOSE TO NEUTRALITY: LABORATORY AND SOLAR PILOT-PLANT REACTOR.

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ABSTRACT

A theoretical and experimental study of the photo-Fenton degradation of herbicide 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) is presented. A kinetic model derived from a reaction sequence is proposed using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source, for conditions of pH close to neutrality. Operating the system under simulated solar radiation, with high radiation level and the highest concentration of hydrogen peroxide (HP), the conversion of 2,4-D after 180 min of reaction was close to 100% over the full range of working temperatures. Moreover, for all the tests performed using the solar reactor, complete destruction of 2,4-D and 2,4-DCP (the main intermediate, 2,4-dichlorophenol) is obtained in only 75 and 120 min of reaction, respectively.

INTRODUCTION

The use of ferric salts in the homogeneous photo-Fenton reaction presents as the main limitation, the narrow pH range for its application. At pH values greater than 3, Fe(III) precipitates as hydroxides [1]. Hence, the objective of this research was the evaluation of the procedure at pH = 5, which is the natural value of 2,4-D active compound at the concentration under study. The kinetic model derived from a reaction sequence and using the ferric oxalate complex as iron source was employed to predict the concentrations of 2,4-D, 2,4-DCP, HP and oxalate (Ox) in a solar pilot plant reactor.

METHODOLOGY

Kinetic experiments were performed in a lab-flat plate reactor of borosilicate glass with external recycle irradiated from one side with a solar simulator. Experimental runs were defined by a 3 level factorial design. The effect of the variables: HP to 2,4-D initial concentration ratios ($R = 7, 28.5$ and 50) and reaction temperatures ($T = 25, 35$ and 50)

°C) on the herbicide degradation was assessed. The solar experimental runs were performed in a pilot-plant solar reactor placed inside a batch recycling system that has a high-flow-rate centrifugal pump and a storage tank. The total volume of the treated solution was 35 L, while the irradiated reactor volume was 6.1 L.

For all tests, the 2,4-D concentration was 30 mg L^{-1} and the $\text{pH} = 5$. Also, to ensure the stabilization of iron in solution throughout the reaction it was necessary to use a molar ratio $\text{Oxa} / \text{Fe} = 10$ (exceeding the stoichiometric value).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A simplified reaction mechanism is summarized in Table 1. The degradation rate expressions of 2,4-D, 2,4-DCP, HP and Ox can be written by using the matrix representation as in eq. 1. For the kinetic studies performed in the lab-scale flat plate reactor, the mass balances and the initial conditions are given by the set of first order, ordinary differential eq. 2 and 3 (matrix notation). The kinetic parameters were estimated from experimental data by applying the nonlinear regression procedure of Newton Gauss-Marquardt (Table 2).

$$\mathbf{R}(x,t) = \mathbf{R}^T(t) + \mathbf{R}^{irr}(x,t) \quad (1) \quad \frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{C}(t) = \mathbf{R}^T(t) + \frac{V_{irr}}{V} \mathbf{R}^{irr}(x,t) \quad (2) \quad \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}^0 \quad t = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} T(t) = \Omega A c q_T(t) - \Gamma [T - T_a(t)] + K \quad (4) \quad T = T^0 \quad t = 0 \quad (5)$$

For the solar reactor, mass (eq. 2 and 3) and thermal energy balances (eq. 4 and 5) are required to predict the species concentrations and the reaction temperatures in the reactor. At this point, values of direct and diffuse solar radiation fluxes reaching the reactor window must be incorporated in the reactor model (SMARTS2) (Conte et al., 2012).

Figure 1 shows experimental data and kinetic model prediction of 2,4-D, 2,4-DCP, HP and Ox relative concentration, for solar experiments at $C_{\text{Ox}}^0 = 0.54 \text{ mM}$ and $C_{\text{Fe(III)}}^0 = 0.054 \text{ mM}$. For $R=50$ ($C_{\text{HP}}^0 = 6.5 \text{ mM}$) the maximum total solar radiation flux between 300-500 nm (q_{Tot}^{inc}) estimated with the SMARTS2 code was $9.58 \times 10^{-8} \text{ E cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and for $R=28.5$ ($C_{\text{HP}}^0 = 3.7 \text{ mM}$) was $1.03 \times 10^{-7} \text{ E cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

For conditions of Figure 1.a (higher incident radiation and higher increased in the operating T , ΔT^{120}) the conversion at 60 min ($x_{2,4-D}^{60}$) was complete. While for a higher dosage of the HP, the $x_{2,4-D}^{60}$ was only 91.5%. Then, it is important to emphasize the influence of the total radiation on the behaviour of the system when using ferrioxalate as catalyst.

Also, a good agreement between the kinetic model and experimental data, for a rather wide range of the operating variables, is observed ($\text{RMSE}_{2,4-D} = 3.61 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mM}$, $\text{RMSE}_{2,4-DCP} = 5.91 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mM}$, $\text{RMSE}_{\text{HP}} = 2.16 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mM}$ and $\text{RMSE}_{\text{Ox}} = 2.45 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mM}$).

Table 1. Reaction scheme of 2,4-D degradation.

Nº	Reaction step
0	$Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} \xrightarrow{h\nu} Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + CO_2 + 1.5C_2O_4^{2-}$
1	$Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} + H_2O_2 \rightarrow Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + 2C_2O_4^{2-} + OH^\bullet + OH^-$
2	$Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + H_2O_2 + 2C_2O_4^{2-} \rightarrow Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} + OH^\bullet + OH^-$
3	$H_2O_2 + OH^\bullet \rightarrow O_2^{\bullet-} + H^+$
4	$2,4-D + OH^\bullet \rightarrow 2,4-DCP$
5	$2,4-DCP + OH^\bullet \rightarrow products$
6	$C_2O_4^{2-} + OH^\bullet \rightarrow 2CO_2 + OH^-$

$$A_1 = \ln(k_{\infty,1}) - \frac{E_1}{R T_{ref}}, B_1 = \frac{E_1}{R T_{ref}} \text{ and } T_{ref} = 298^\circ K$$

Table 2. Estimated kinetic parameters

Param.	Value	Units
A_1	-2.76	-
B_1	4.37	-
k_2^*	3.10×10^4	$M^{-1} s^{-1}$
k_3	3.76×10^7	$M^{-1} s^{-1}$
k_4^*	3.00×10^9	$M^{-1} s^{-1}$
k_5	2.38×10^{10}	$M^{-1} s^{-1}$
k_6^*	7.70×10^6	$M^{-1} s^{-1}$
$\bar{\Phi}_{Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4)}$	1.21	$mol E^{-1}$
$\bar{\Phi}_{C_2O_4^{2-}}$	1.05	$mol E^{-1}$

(* taken from the specific literature)

Figure 1. Model and experimental solar results for 2,4-D, 2,4-DCP, HP and Ox concentrations. (a) $R=28.5$, $T^0=27.4^\circ C$, $\Delta T^{120}=11.3^\circ C$ (b) $R=50$, $T^0=24.8^\circ C$, $\Delta T^{120}=9.3^\circ C$. Keys: (—) Model results, (o) 2,4-D, (◊) 2,4-DCP, (+) HP, (*) Ox.

CONCLUSIONS

A theoretical and experimental study of the homogeneous photo-Fenton degradation of the herbicide 2,4-D is presented. A simplified kinetic model derived from a reaction sequence was proposed using the ferric oxalate complex as iron source for conditions of pH close to neutrality. A good agreement between kinetic model results and experimental data was observed.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the work entitled

*“PHOTO-FENTON DEGRADATION OF A HERBICIDE USING THE FERRIOXALATE COMPLEX FOR pH CONDITIONS CLOSE TO NEUTRALITY: LABORATORY AND SOLAR PILOT-PLANT REACTOR” and authored by **Leandro O. Conte; Agustina V. Schenone; Orlando M. Alfano** was presented at the VIII EPOA and II CIPOA as Oral presentation.*

Camilla Costa de Amorim
Chairwoman of VIII EPOA

Vitor Jorge Pais Vilar
Chairman of II CIPOA

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that

Leandro Oscar Conte

has attended the VIII Meeting on Environmental Applications of Advanced Oxidation Processes
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